

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Catalysed Oxidation of Benzylamine by Hexacyanoferrate(III) in Alkaline Medium

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The kinetics of ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of benzylamine by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium has been carried out. The reaction has been observed to be zero order with respect to oxidant and first order at lower concentrations of substrate and alkali tending towards zero order at their higher concentrations. Further, with respect to ruthenium(III), the order has been observed to be unity. A probable mechanism explaining all the observed results has been postulated. The activation parameters have been calculated.

THE present work is an extension of the previous work¹ carried on the kinetics and mechanism of ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of benzylalcohol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in alkaline medium. However, one observable difference in the kinetics of benzylalcohol and benzylamine is with respect to hydroxyl ion concentration. In the case of benzylalcohol, the reaction rate first increases with the increasing concentration of hydroxyl ion at their lower concentration, reaches a maximum and then decreases with increasing hydroxide ion concentration. On the other hand, in the case of benzylamine, the reaction has been observed to be first order at lower concentrations of alkali tending towards zero order at higher concentrations. This has necessitated the proposal of a mechanism which is different from the one suggested in the case of benzylalcohol.

Experimental

The experimental procedure to study the progress of the reaction is the same as the one described earlier¹. The materials employed in the investigation were of A.R. grade.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data for the reaction rate with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion variation are presented in Table 1. The ionic strength of the medium was kept constant throughout the investigation. The constancy of $-dc/dt$ values for about ten-fold excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion at constant concentra-

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF FERRICYANIDE CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

$[NaOH]=3.00 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[Benzylamine]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 $[RuCl_3]=2.980 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu=0.50 M$

$[K_2Fe(ON)_6] \times 10^3 M$	$(\frac{-dc}{dt}) \times 10^4$ M min ⁻¹
1.00	1.40
2.00	1.40
3.00	1.40
4.00	1.60
5.00	1.70
6.00	1.70
8.00	2.00
10.00	2.00

tions of other reactants indicates a zero order reaction with respect to the oxidant.

At constant concentrations of the catalyst, hydroxyl ion and the oxidant, the plots of $-dc/dt$ vs benzylamine concentration show first order kinetics at lower concentrations tending towards zero order kinetics at higher concentrations (Fig. 1A). The variation of reaction rate with hydroxyl ion concentration follows the same trend as observed in case of the substrate (Fig. 1B). Finally, a plot of the reaction rate vs concentration of ruthenium(III) has been found to be linear, thereby indicating a first order kinetics with respect to ruthenium(III) (Fig. 2).

On the basis of the above experimental results a probable rate law for the oxidation of benzylamine at the lower concentration of the reactants may be

Fig. 1A. Plot of $-dc/dt$ vs [Benzylamine]. $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[NaOH] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[RuCl_3] = 4.76 \times 10^{-7}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35° .
 B. Plot of $-dc/dt$ against $[NaOH]$. $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[Benzylamine] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[RuCl_3] = 2.38 \times 10^{-7}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35° .

Fig. 2. Effect of variation of catalyst ruthenium(III) chloride on the reaction rate.
 $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[NaOH] = 3.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $[Benzylamine] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35° .

proposed as follows.

The different steps in the postulated mechanism of the ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of benzylamine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) may be shown as follows.

In the above scheme of oxidation of benzylamine the reactive species of ruthenium(III) in aqueous alkaline medium directly reacts with the substrate molecule to give intermediate complex which slowly disproportionates to give the final reaction product and the hydride species of ruthenium(III). It has been observed that transition metal complexes are good abstracting agents for the hydride ion^{2,3}. They can adequately abstract a hydride ion even from a hydrogen molecule. In acidic medium the abstraction of a hydride ion from α -carbon atom of 2-propanol has also been observed⁴. In a similar manner studies have been performed and it was concluded that hydride ion transfer takes place from the α -carbon atom of the alcohol or alkoxide ion to the metal atom^{5,6}. This gives sufficient evidence that hydride ion transfer will take place during the course of the oxidation of the above mentioned substrate by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium using ruthenium(III)-chloride as a homogeneous catalyst.

In the last step, the ruthenium(III) hydride species is reoxidised to its original ruthenium(III) reactive species $[Ru(H_2O)_5OH]^{2+}$. Step (3) in the above proposed scheme is the rate determining step. Hence,

Making use of steps (1) and (2), expression (5) reduces to,

Considering the equilibrium condition in steps (1) and (2) and knowing that,

The rate law (6) reduces to

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} = \frac{k'K_1K_2[Substrate][OH^-][Ru^{III}]_T}{1 + K_1[OH^-] + K_1K_2[Substrate][OH^-]} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} = \frac{k'K_1K_2[Substrate][OH^-][Ru^{III}]_T}{1 + K_1[OH^-](1 + K_2[Substrate])} \quad (8)$$

At lower concentrations of substrate, the inequality $1 \gg K_2[S]$ may be assumed to hold good and the

rate law (8) becomes

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = \frac{k'K_1K_2[\text{Substrate}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_T}{1+K_1[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) shows first order kinetics with respect to substrate at lower concentrations (Fig. 1A).

Further at low concentrations of alkali, the inequality $1 \gg K_1[\text{OH}^-]$ may be assumed to be valid and under this condition equation (9) takes the form

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = k'K_1K_2[\text{Substrate}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_T \quad (10)$$

The rate law (10) is apparently consistent with the observed first order kinetics with respect to hydroxyl ion concentration at lower concentrations. However, at higher hydroxide ion concentrations, the inequality $K_1[\text{OH}^-] \gg 1$ would be supposed to be valid and under this condition equation (9) takes the form,

$$\frac{-b}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = k'K_2[\text{Substrate}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_T \quad (11)$$

Rate law (11) evidently accounts for the zero order kinetics with respect to hydroxyl ion at higher concentrations.

Equation (8) at constant $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_T$ becomes

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = \frac{k'K_1K_2[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]}{1+K_1[\text{OH}^-]+K_1K_2[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (12)$$

The reciprocal of equation (12) would give,

$$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{[\text{S}] \left[\frac{1}{k'K_1K_2[\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{k'K_2} \right]} + \frac{1}{k'} \quad (13)$$

The plot of $(\text{Rate})^{-1}$ vs $(\text{benzylamine})^{-1}$ has been found to be linear with the intercept on Y-axis (Fig. 3).

Fig 3. Plot of $(-dc/dt)^{-1}$ vs $[\text{Benzylamine}]^{-1}$. $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 3.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_6] = 2.38 \times 10^{-7}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35° .

On the basis of equation (13), in the plot of $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $1/[\text{Substrate}]$ at constant $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Fig. 3) the intercept corresponds to $1/k'$ from which the value of k' comes out to be 13.3×10^{-8} min $^{-1}$ at 35° . Similarly, on the basis of equation (12), the plot of $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ at constant substrate

concentration will give the slope equal to $\frac{1}{k'K_1K_2[\text{S}]}$

and the intercept equivalent to $\frac{1}{k'K_2[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k'}$. With

the help of the slope and intercept of the plot of $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ at constant substrate concentration

Fig. 4. Plot of $(-dc/dt)^{-1}$ vs $1/[\text{OH}]$.

[A]: $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_6] = 2.38 \times 10^{-7}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35°
 [B]: $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_6] = 4.76 \times 10^{-7}$ M, $\mu = 0.50$ M, temp. = 35° .

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substrate	Catalyst	Temp. 35°				
		k _s sec ⁻¹	ΔE kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	A	ΔS/R e
Benzylamine	RuCl ₃	0.75 × 10 ⁻⁵	50.07	-189.099	8.14 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.33 × 10 ⁻¹⁰

shown in Fig. 4, the calculated values of K_1 and K_2 come out to be 59.05 and 55.5, respectively. On the basis of calculated K_1 and K_2 values and also the minimum and maximum concentration of alkali and substrate used in the present work, the three presumptions, namely $1 \gg K_2[S]$ at lower substrate concentration, $1 \gg K_1[OH^-]$ at low concentration of alkali and $K_1[OH^-] \gg 1$ at higher concentration of alkali can be verified. It may be mentioned that the lower substrate concentration taken in present catalysed oxidation of benzylamine has been $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ (not shown in Fig. 1A) and the lowest and highest concentration of NaOH used, has been 0.5×10^{-2} and $20 \times 10^{-2} M$, respectively (not shown in Fig. 1B).

Thus, the above evidences support the postulated mechanism.

Stoichiometry and product study : The number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion consumed by one mole of benzylamine was determined by taking a number of reaction mixtures in which the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was kept ten times larger than that of the organic substrate. After completion of the reaction, the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) ion produced was estimated in different sets of experiments by the usual method^{7,8}. In each set, it was found that one mole of benzylamine required 2 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. We, therefore, conclude that the final oxidation

product would be benzaldehyde. The reaction mixture was distilled after completion of the reaction and the distillate were collected at 177°. The distillate gave a positive test of aldehyde with Schiff's reagent. On oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate and further acidification by hydrochloric acid a white precipitate of benzoic acid is formed. This also supports that the distillate obtained at 177° is nothing but benzaldehyde.

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